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(Re)thinking Resilience

Climate change as a challenge in the protection of historical architecture.

Case study on revitalization and adaptation to climate changes of traditional rural objects.

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ABSTRACT: Regardless of the problems with climate change mitigation, the urgent need for adaptation measures cannot be overlooked; Not all negative elements of anthropogenic pressure will be eliminated in the future. In such a complicated matter as spatial development, it is quite a challenge. It should be realized that due to the specificity of the construction industry, the architectural substance, as a rule, is implemented for many decades. The article is a case study of a historical, vernacular building from the 19th century in the West Pomeranian Voivodeship in Poland. On the one hand, the applied solutions to save historical buildings protected by law as heritage are a response to the social needs of the local community, and on the other hand, they are a way of adapting historical architecture to the progressing climate change, which makes it possible to extend its life cycle and thus minimize the carbon footprint of the investment. The presented solutions use circular design activities and can be easily scaled up to other similar historical objects, so they can become an effective tool for adapting to climate change, and due to the use of recycled materials – also a tool for mitigating climate change.

KEYWORDS: Circular designing, climate adaptation, carbon neutral, clay building, heritage

1. INTRODUCTION

In August 2021, the first of three parts of the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, on the physical basis of climate change, was published, which is a kind of summary of the current state, projected scenarios of its changes and the related adaptive possibilities of modern societies. According to the report, it is clear that "human activity has led to global warming at a rate not seen in at least the last 2,000 years." All signatories to the Paris Agreement [1] agree in principle that the observed increase in greenhouse gas concentrations since about 1750 is indisputably caused by human activity. Although published in 2011 Fifth Report required each party to reduce emissions, these concentrations continued to rise, reaching an annual average of 410 ppm in 2019. Currently, the CO₂ concentration at NOAA's Mauna Loa observatory is already around 422.14 ppm [2], which means that with the climate sensitivity currently established, the safe warming threshold of 1.5°C would be exceeded by mid-2029 [3]; It would have been, if it were not for the fact that the global distribution of temperatures is influenced by many factors, both natural and anthropogenic. The complexity of these processes and a number of climate couplings resulted in the warming level of 1.5°C already being exceeded by the end of 2023 [4]. In the author's opinion, this is undoubtedly the greatest failure from the point of view of contemporary post-industrial civilization, which cannot be ignored without comment. Regardless of the state of climate imbalances and

projected SSP [5] scenarios, it is necessary to expect the need for urgent action to slow down the discussed changes in every area of human activity, including construction.

In addition to the climate change mitigation problems mentioned in the report, the urgent need for adaptation cannot be overlooked, which is a natural consequence of exceeding the target of a safe level of global warming a decade earlier than forecast. Not all negative elements of anthropogenic pressure will be eliminated soon. In such a complicated and complex matter as spatial planning, this is quite a challenge, as confirmed by The World Heritage Committee at its 29th session in 2005 [6]. It should be realized that due to the specificity of the construction industry, the architectural substance is usually implemented over many decades. In this context, it is important to note that the historical architecture that is of interest to the author was created at a time when climate change was out of the question [7] and in no way corresponds to the dynamically developing adaptation needs in this area. What is more, historical buildings are very often objects of high cultural and aesthetic value, bound by specific legal regulations and conservation protection. Such a situation narrows the repertoire of possible adaptation measures.

2. AGEING MODERNITY – ARCHITECTURE AS A FUNCTION OF TIME

Historical architecture is valuable for many reasons, but it is also burdened with the rigor of heritage conservation, where it is often difficult to achieve adequacy in terms of adaptation requirements. According to the author, the current state of climate imbalance, which is a consequence of progressing climate change, shows that the problem of adaptation of traditional vernacular architecture to the "new, greenhouse" reality is an important topic, although it is rarely discussed in science in a comprehensive way [8,9]. In addition to the collection of "iconic" buildings that create a context in the historical substance of the city, whose cultural values are indisputable, there are still old buildings that are not under strict protection. Their modernization is not so strictly regulated by the conditions of conservation protection. These buildings also create a context, although the lack of strict legal protection means that the quality of the renovations carried out and the set of solutions used can leave much to be desired, thus reducing their cultural and aesthetic attractiveness. The author deliberately narrows down the issues to vernacular architecture, without dealing with the entire spectrum of adaptations of historical buildings. Regional and vernacular architecture protected only within the framework of the municipal (local) heritage register is a large part of protected objects, although their value is often underestimated, and the possibilities of increasing their value, including modernization activities, fall on the shoulders of private investors. This can result in the risk of losing authenticity and, so, cultural values. In the discussed area of Poland (West Pomeranian Voivodeship), rural buildings are often the legacy of many years of not investing in this region of the country, which builds the image of the voivodeship as a problem area in systemic terms. Underinvestment in local communities and a deep social and economic crisis of local communities in small West Pomeranian villages are among the main causes of the collapse in the context of spatial investment in the area.

Adaptation to potential climate changes projected in the next few decades will therefore require not only the construction of a new (ecological) architectural substance, but also the largely renewal of existing, often historic architecture built with the use of traditional technology.

Only architecture that is adequate to the expected functional parameters, aesthetic, but also energy-efficient and safe in terms of construction will be able to be considered socially attractive and will have a chance to exist in the structure of villages and cities. This, in turn, is a real tool for extending its life cycle, which is an important aspect from the point of view of reducing emissions of the construction industry. In the case of their modernization and

adaptation to new conditions (including climatic conditions), it is natural that greenhouse gas emissions will appear because of investment activities. It's also important to note that embodied carbon emissions are already neutralised after 100 years; not demolishing that historical architecture means, in fact, the possibility of omitting a new investment and its new carbon footprint.

In conclusion, according to the author, the aging of architecture is a complex function of many factors. Time as a variable in architecture and its impact on the environmental balance of a project is a well-known problem, but very rarely addressed in the context of traditional architecture. Historically, time was a "transparent" architectural element (its impact was not noticeable until the object was old enough to collapse). Nowadays, the time factor is consciously considered as a decisive element for the profitability of an investment. In order to properly carry out the revitalization of the historical architectural substance, it is necessary to realize that historical buildings were under the influence of the same laws of physics, this is due to their use, construction processes, previously completed renovations and reconstructions, and the specificity of the technologies used. Now they need an individual approach each time. After all, there are many examples where poorly applied modern technologies have led to the destruction of a historic building, and the matter is further complicated by two factors: the first is the passage of time, which can affect the durability of individual elements of the building, and the second is the modularity of "layers" expressed in their technical reliability [10].

3. SUBJECT MATTER AND SCOPE OF RESEARCH

The article is a case study of a historic, vernacular building, where the applied solutions to save the historic buildings could then be scaled up to other similar objects. In the area of the West Pomeranian Voivodeship and in areas with a similar construction tradition, there are a lot of analogous buildings that will be destroyed and replaced with a new architectural substance generating an added burden on the carbon dioxide budget, if they are not renovated. If their social attractiveness is increased, life cycle will be extended. The applied solutions are aimed at extending the life cycle of the building by giving it a new function, new technical and economic values, and thus making it an attractive object. This will mean cutting the demolition phase of life cycle and replacing the building with a new structure. In this way, the carbon footprint of the investment process is minimized while keeping the spatial context of the village and its aesthetic and cultural values. CO₂ stays in the atmosphere for about 100 years, so leaving a historic building minimizes the carbon footprint.

In addition, the solutions applied and described in this article are also aimed at adapting the facility to new threats caused by climate change, such as reduced snow cover in winter and the resulting increased risk of ground freezing and destruction of historical foundations. Some of the solutions are based on the "Natural Based Infrastructure" principle [11], promoted by UNEP as solutions with a high potential for mitigating climate change. The preservation of vernacular architecture and thus the preservation of its cultural values as an element of heritage is quite a challenge in the face of dynamically changing expectations in terms of adequacy of functions and utility values. The challenge will be to preserve historical values while optimizing the functional layout to contemporary expectations and additionally protecting the existing spatial structure against the potential impact of climate change, minimizing the carbon footprint of the investment. Taken together, all these challenges appear to be complex and fraught with a high risk of uncertainty. Szymanowska-Gwizdz et al. rightly point out [12] that the modification of historic buildings must consider the postulates of preserving historical and cultural values. In the author's opinion, the changing reality due to the ongoing climate processes also requires considering these new aspects in architecture – including the revitalized one.

The described building was built in the second half of the 19th century, around the years 1850-1870. In this case, due to the period of construction and the fact that it has not been renovated practically since 1911. This gives grounds to assume that in the case of this investment, it will be necessary to modernize not only the basic elements of the installation equipment of the facility or the external structure (sheathing, window and door joinery, roof sheathing), but also to verify the condition of the main supporting structure [fig. 2].

As mentioned earlier, in the author's opinion, each building should be considered in a time module corresponding to the usability of the individual layers of the building described below [13], while taking into account contemporary conditions (including climatic conditions).

Figure 1: Diagram of time periods in architecture vs climate changes.

Figure 2: Building before renovation, source: M. Okła

To understand the extent of interference in the existing structure of featured building, it is necessary to look at the specifics of the frame structure and understand its operation. The mullion and transom structures (half-timbered) are one of the frame structures that use wood as a material for making load-bearing elements. The base here are vertical load-bearing columns always made of a single element, embedded in the sockets of the foundation laid horizontally on the foundation and fastened with a horizontal cap at the height of the ceiling with glazing.¹ Between the vertical elements there are horizontal transom elements, fixed in sockets made in wooden posts.² In the corners of the walls, there are additionally braces stiffening the structure and protecting the entire structural system against horizontal forces, m.in. from the wind (gable facades).

The loads from the roof, ceiling and walls were fully transferred to the foundation in half-timbered structure through a continuous ground beam.

This is quite an important structural assumption, taking into account the fact that in many cases (including the one discussed) these foundations were made of stones, without the use of a cement-based binder, and after such a long time of using the building, the wooden structure of the half-timbered wall is in poor technical condition [fig.3]. Two important conclusions can be drawn from the analyses of the existing structure of the building carried out in the years 2017-2021.

¹ A slab is a ceiling filling consisting of a mixture of clay and ash, sometimes vegetable additives as an insulating material; Despite its original function, which was to fill and stiffen the ceiling, it is also worth mentioning the additional role of the glazing as a kind of heat accumulator, which stored the surplus heat from the unused attic in the summer and gave it back in the transitional period. The ash in the glaze had an antiseptic function.

Figure 3: Building before renovation, source: author

1. More than 150 years of use of the building led to damage (deformation) of the foundation [see fig.2]; In addition, a foundation that was too shallow caused it to undergo displacements related to soil comparison and freezing processes. After all, the technical knowledge of that time did not focus on the depth of the foundation, but rather on counteracting the capillary rising of moisture through the walls [14], which, according to the currently available knowledge, was one of the biggest problems of the construction industry at that time [15].

2. The conclusion from the conducted analyses was the urgent need to carry out renovation works aimed at strengthening or possible replacement of the timber frame structure while protecting the foundation against freezing [fig.6]. In addition, these works should respond in advance to the projected climate changes while maximizing the authenticity of the building and minimizing the carbon footprint of the renovation phase. What is more, in order for these activities to be scalable to other investments in the future, the renovation must also be financially rational. The redevelopment process must therefore take all these guidelines into account and not be a mere compromise.

4. CHALLENGES

As Colette pointed out [16] *“Climate change is primarily a threat that has physical impacts. But, in turn, these effects have societal and cultural consequences. When it comes to cultural ‘dynamic’ heritage – i.e. buildings and landscapes where people live, work, worship, and socialize – it is important to underline the cultural consequences. These consequences can be derived from the degradation of the property under consideration.”*

When talking about contemporary climate challenges, we have in mind a whole set of potential threats [17], although in general we should pay attention to three basic aspects – adaptation to climate change, mitigation of climate change and development of the circular economy – all three elements have been regulated for several years by the European Union regulations [18]. In the context

of historical buildings, the threat associated with changing climate parameters may undoubtedly be the inadequacy of the foundation level of the building to the changing specific properties of winter periods.

4.1. FREEZING OF THE BASEMENT OF THE BUILDING

The visible constant trend of climate change was the basis for the EU directive M/515 [19], which, as Godlewski points out [20], indicates the need to *“build and maintain more climate-resilient infrastructure by changing and adapting the provisions of the standards used in the construction industry”*. Paradoxically, this is not due to a decrease in average temperatures, but to the progressing warming of the climate, i.e., an increase in global temperatures and the disappearance of snow cover. Ground covered by a layer of snow freezes to a much lower depth due to the insulating properties of snow. The values of the maximum position of the zero isotherm in the ground not covered by snow are more than twice as deep as in the case of the ground covered by snow cover, which is confirmed by research conducted over the years by Gródecki [21] and Ickiewicz [22]. This is quite significant, because with the warming of winters, the number of days with snow cover in Poland is decreasing; according to IMGW data, in the period 1961-2020 the number of days with snow cover decreased on average from 63.9 to 39.5 [23]. The negative impact of changing climate parameters during winter on architectural heritage has also been highlighted as an important aspect by UNESCO [24] and United Nations Environment Programme in *Climate Leadership* programme [25].

In the analysed historical building, a decision was made to adapt to the changing reality in two ways: to protect the foundations against both freezing and heat energy losses, and to relieve the existing half-timbered structure of the walls. The first one is aimed at protecting the foundation against the destructive effects of frost and increasing the energy efficiency of the building, thus increasing the attractiveness of the building in the economic aspect. The second is to relieve the external wall and transfer the loads from the roof to the new wooden columns. The stone foundations are too shallow, and there is no rational way to sink them without losing the authenticity of the building; It is also impossible to pick up ground level around a building (covering foundations) without losing its aesthetic and historical value. For this reason, it was decided to use wooden columns and make them an added, independent structure inside the building to relieve the external walls. The columns were placed on new foundations inside the building (fig.6), at a depth that considers the increased impact of frost. These poles were made of wood obtained from the demolition of a barn from the same time, so that the newly created structure does not stand out from the original

substance. In addition, this measure significantly reduced the carbon footprint of direct emissions. The construction works were analysed following the ISO 14064 standard, and obtaining material from the demolition of another facility is a conscious action in the field of circular economy [26], influencing the improvement of the MRP factor³. The problem of freezing foundations has not been noticed for years. In old buildings, heat losses were enormous, although the cost (financial and environmental) of heating was low at that time. Large heat losses through the lower part of the walls and through the stone strip footing caused the ground to heat up and move the frozen zone away from the structure (fig.4).

The problem of freezing appeared at the time of making a concrete band "combined" with a stone bench, which was to stabilize the structure of the building (XXth century) and when the floor and external wall were insulated (fig.5).

Figure 4: Diagram of the existing foundation – original layout from the 19th century, source: author

Actions aimed at increasing energy efficiency resulted in a reduction in heat losses to the ground, and thus increased the risk of freezing of the foundations. Previously, excessive heat emission *de facto* moved the "cold" zone further away from the foundation. Bearing in mind the fact that the disappearing snow layer due to climate change may result in increased freezing, it was decided to intervene in the form of horizontal insulation of the concrete band. This will keep the frost away from the shallow stone bench (fig. 6).

Figure 5: Diagram of the foundation after modernization; 1960, source: author

³ MRP – Materials Reusability Potential indicator – one of the factors of circularity of architecture.

Figure 6: Diagram of the foundation after modernization; 2020, source: author

The described activities were carried out after analysing various environmental scenarios of the renovation and assessing the CO₂ budget. In addition, both the materials for the construction of the columns, the edge elements and the insulation of the foundations come from recycling (see MRP indicator), and the stone covering of the thermal insulation was made of local stones, minimizing ADP factor⁴ of the investment.

5. CONCLUSION

In the author's opinion, the activities in the field of renovation and reconstruction of historic nineteenth-century residential buildings described in the case study show that with precise and appropriate use of techniques and knowledge of traditional methods of building construction, it is possible to carry out investments in a way that is sensitive to the issues of respect for cultural heritage and aspects of beauty in rural space. At the same time, in a manner adequate to the modern needs of adaptation to climate change, considering the entire life cycle of the building to minimize the carbon footprint of the investment.

Figure 8, 9: Insulation of the foundation following the schemes (after/during work); Condition approx. 2020, source: author

According to the author, such a comprehensive approach to the problem would allow to scale up that way of operation for future investments of a similar nature, so that the adaptation of traditional

⁴ ADP – Abiotic Depletion Potential.

architecture to new climatic conditions could become a specific tool for mitigating climate change.

Figure 10: The building after rebuilding, source: author

(Carbon footprint of article: 0,835kg CO₂e)

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